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Original Research Article

Pattern of Maxillofacial Trauma at tertiary Healthcare Centre of Central Uttar Pradesh- A Retrospective Study.

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Abstract:

Background: The faciomaxillary region, being highly exposed, is prone to trauma. Maxillofacial injuries pose a significant challenge in emergency care, with varied aetiology influenced by geographic, cultural, and socioeconomic factors. This study aimed to assess the pattern, aetiology, intubation methods, associated complications, and outcomes of maxillofacial trauma in a tertiary care hospital in central Uttar Pradesh.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective hospital-based study was conducted at Chandra Dental College & Hospital, Barabanki, including 243 patients aged 15–60 years admitted with maxillofacial fractures between January 2021 and December 2023. Data on demographics,

fracture type, aetiology, concomitant injuries, intubation methods, and post-operative outcomes were collected from hospital records and analysed statistically.

Results: The mean age of patients was 39.9 ± 12.4 years, with males predominating (68.7%). Road traffic accidents were the leading cause (69.5%), followed by falls (13.99%), assaults (8.6%), and sports injuries (6.5%). Head injuries were the most common associated trauma (60.5%). Among maxillary and midfacial fractures, zygomaticomaxillary complex fractures were most frequent (67.07%), while in mandibular fractures, condylar (31.27%) and parasymphysis (27.98%) fractures predominated. Naso-endotracheal intubation was the primary airway management technique (88.06%), with submental intubation used in 11.93% of cases. Post-operative complications included infection (20.16%), malocclusion (13.99%), and plate loosening (13.99%), whereas uneventful healing was observed in 37.86% of patients.

Conclusion: Maxillofacial trauma in central Uttar Pradesh predominantly affects middle-aged males, with road traffic accidents as the leading cause. ZMC and condylar fractures are most common. Naso-endotracheal intubation remains the preferred method, while infection and malocclusion are the primary postoperative concerns. These findings emphasize the need for preventive strategies and optimized post-operative care to improve patient outcomes.

Key words: Maxillofacial trauma, Zygomaticomaxillary complex fracture, Mandibular fracture, Road traffic accident, Naso-endotracheal intubation

Introduction

The maxillofacial region consists of both soft and bony tissues and is one of the most exposed parts of the human body, making it highly susceptible to trauma. Such injuries constitute a significant and potentially life-threatening concern in both developing and developed countries, accounting for approximately 7.4% to 8.7% of all emergency medical cases.^{1,2} The incidence of maxillofacial trauma is on the rise and is frequently observed in cases of assaults, emergencies, and accidents reported to hospitals. These injuries constitute a significant portion of medico-legal cases encountered in trauma and emergency settings.³ The etiology of maxillofacial trauma varies across different geographic regions and even within localities of the same area. These variations are largely influenced by environmental factors, cultural practices, and the socioeconomic status of individuals affected by orofacial injuries.⁴ A thorough and systematic evaluation of maxillofacial fractures and trauma within a specific locality can help identify prevailing injury patterns and offer valuable insights for developing effective preventive strategies to reduce the incidence of such injuries.⁵ Several previous

studies have examined the etiology and severity of maxillofacial injuries, reporting variations in incidence across different regions of India and highlighting their strong association with road traffic accidents and assaults. However, there is limited and insufficient data available from the central region of Uttar Pradesh. Hence, the present study aims to evaluate the pattern, etiology, mode of intubation, associated complications, and treatment outcomes of maxillofacial trauma cases managed at a tertiary care hospital in central Uttar Pradesh. Additionally, it seeks to provide a clearer understanding of the demographics and epidemiological characteristics of maxillofacial injuries in this region.

Materials and Methods:

Study design: Retrospective Hospital based study

Place of study: Chandra Dental College & Hospital, Barabanki

Aims and Objectives:

1. To determine the prevalence and assess the pattern, etiology, intubation mode, associated complications, and outcomes following the management of maxillofacial trauma.
2. To obtain a clear picture of demographics, epidemiology, and etiology of maxillofacial injuries.

The study subjects were recruited from hospital records of last three years from January 2021 to December 2024 for the patients admitted to Department of oral & Maxillofacial Surgery at Chandra Dental College and Hospital, Barabanki and were diagnosed with maxillofacial fracture post-surgery. After obtaining ethical clearance from the ethical committee of the Institute, total 243 patients, both males and females in the age group of 15-60 years were assessed during these three years.

Methodology:

Inclusion criteria:

1. Subjects with a confirmatory diagnosis of maxillofacial both clinically as well as radio-graphically.
2. Subjects with history of trauma,
3. Subjects treated for fracture at the institution,
4. Subjects with age group of 15-60 years, and

5. Subjects giving consent to participate.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Subjects whose information was not available or incomplete.
2. Subjects beyond age group of 15-60 years, and
3. Subjects not giving consent to participate.

Data collection included a detailed medical history encompassing demographic information, radiographic findings, associated injuries, and the etiology of fractures. The specific fracture sites involving both the maxilla and mandible were documented. Additionally, the type of intubation employed and postoperative evaluations were recorded, along with any reported postoperative complications.

Data analysis

The collected data were statistically analysed to derive the results. Findings were presented in terms of percentages, frequencies, means, and standard deviations. Correlation and Chi-square tests were also applied for statistical evaluation.

Observations & Results:

A total of 243 study subjects of maxillofacial injuries were included over the three-year study period (2021–2023). The highest number of subjects were recorded in 2023 (85; 35%), followed by 2022 (82; 33.7%) and 2021 (76; 31.3%). There was a gradual increase in the number of subjects each year. (Table 1)

Table1: Year wise distribution of the study subjects

S. No	Year	No. of Subjects (n)
1.	2021	76
2.	2022	82
3.	2023	85
Total		243

The study subjects ranged in age from 15 to 60 years, with a mean age of 39.9 ± 12.4 years, indicating a predominance of middle-aged individuals. The majority of maxillofacial injuries persons belonged to the 26–35 years age group (32.5%, $n = 79$), followed by 41–45 years (22.22%, $n = 54$) and 15–25 years (20.57%, $n = 50$). Fewer persons were observed in the 46–55 years (5.8%) and 55–60 years (2.8%) categories. This distribution shows that most subjects were within the productive working-age population, reflecting the age pattern typically affected or represented in the study context. (Table 2)

Table 2: Demographic characteristics of the study subjects

S. No	Characteristics	Percentage (%)	Number (n)
1	Mean Age	39.9±12.4 years	
2	Age Range (in years)	15-60	
a	15-25	20.57	50
b	26-35	32.5	79
c	36-40	16	39
d	41-45	22.22	54
d	46-55	5.8	14
e	55-60	2.8	7
3	Gender		
a	Males	68.72	167
b	Females	31.27	76
4	Fracture Cause		
a	Road Traffic Accidents	69.5	169
b	Fall from Height	13.99	34
c	Assault	8.6	21
d	Sports Injuries	6.5	16

e	Alcohol Influence	2.05	5
5	Concomitant Injuries		
a	Head Injuries	60.5	147
b	Pelvis	3.7	9
c	Chest	10.6	26
d	Spine	2.05	5
e	Orthopaedic	16.04	39
f	Abdomen	6.9	17

In the present study, a male predominance was observed among the participants. Of the total cases, 68.72% (n = 167) were males, whereas 31.27% (n = 76) were females. The male-to-female ratio was approximately 2.2:1, indicating a significantly higher incidence among males compared to females. (Table 2)

Road traffic accidents (RTAs) were identified as the most common cause of maxillofacial fractures, accounting for 69.5% (n = 169) of the cases. This was followed by falls from height in 13.99% (n = 34), assaults in 8.6% (n = 21), and sports-related injuries in 6.5% (n = 16) of the cases. Alcohol influence was implicated in 2.05% (n = 5) of patients. The findings indicate that RTAs remain the predominant etiological factor, highlighting the ongoing need for improved road safety measures and public awareness. (Table 2)

Among the study population, concomitant injuries were frequently associated with facial fractures. Head injuries were the most common, observed in 60.5% (n = 147) of the cases. This was followed by orthopaedic injuries in 16.04% (n = 39), chest injuries in 10.6% (n = 26), and abdominal injuries in 6.9% (n = 17). Pelvic injuries were reported in 3.7% (n = 9), while spinal injuries accounted for 2.05% (n = 5) of the cases. These findings suggest that head and skeletal

injuries are the most common associated injuries in patients with maxillofacial fractures, emphasizing the importance of a multidisciplinary approach in initial trauma evaluation and management. (Table 2)

The mean percentage distribution of maxillary and midfacial fractures was $24.98 \pm 27.86\%$. Among these, zygomaticomaxillary complex (ZMC) fractures were the most prevalent, accounting for 67.07% (n = 163) of all maxillary and midfacial fractures. Le Fort II fractures were observed in 20.16% (n = 49), followed by Le Fort III fractures in 7.8% (n = 19), and Le Fort I fractures in 4.9% (n = 12) of cases. The distribution showed a strong positive correlation ($r = 1.0$) between the number of cases and percentage representation, indicating proportional consistency. The predominance of ZMC fractures suggests their greater vulnerability due to anatomical prominence and direct exposure to impact forces, making it highly susceptible to trauma—particularly from road traffic accidents. (Table 3)

Table 3: Sites associated with the maxillofacial trauma in study subjects

S. No	Fractures	Percentage	Number (n)
1.	Maxillary and midfacial Fractures		
a	Le Fort I	4.9	12
b	Le Fort II	20.16	49
c	Le Fort III	7.8	19
d	ZMC fracture	67.07	163
2.	Mandibular Fractures		
a	Angle	22.22	54
b	Body	13.99	34
c	Parasymphysis	27.98	68
d	Condyle	31.27	76
e	Ramus	2.05	5
f	Symphysis	2.88	7
3.	Pan facial fractures	3.2	8

In the present study, mandibular fractures were the most frequently encountered facial fractures. The mean distribution of fracture types was $14.51 \pm 11.79\%$. Among these, condylar fractures were the most common (31.27%, n = 76), followed by parasymphysis (27.98%, n = 68) and angle fractures (22.22%, n = 54). Body (13.99%, n = 34), symphysis (2.88%, n = 7), and ramus fractures (2.05%, n = 5) were less frequent. Additionally, panfacial fractures were reported in 3.2% (n = 8) of cases. A strong positive correlation ($r = 1.0$) was noted between the percentage and number of cases. These findings indicate that condylar and parasymphysis regions are the most vulnerable sites in mandibular trauma, possibly due to the concentration of stress transmission and the biomechanical characteristics of the mandible during impact. (Table 3)

In the present study, naso-endotracheal intubation was the most frequently employed method for airway management among patients with maxillofacial trauma, accounting for 88.06% (n = 214) of cases. Submental intubation was utilized in 11.93% (n = 29) of patients, primarily in situations where naso-endotracheal intubation was contraindicated due to midfacial fractures or base-of-skull involvement. These findings indicate that naso-endotracheal intubation remains the preferred and most practical approach for securing the airway in maxillofacial trauma cases, while submental intubation serves as a valuable alternative in selected cases where nasal or oral routes are unsuitable. (Table 4)

Table 4: Type of Intubation performed in subjects with maxillofacial trauma

S. No.	Intubation	Percentage	Number (n)
1.	Naso endotracheal intubation	88.06	214
2.	Sub mental Intubation	11.93	29

The mean percentage of post-operative outcomes was $11.11 \pm 11.82\%$. Among the various complications, uneventful healing was observed in the majority of cases (37.86%, n = 92). Among adverse outcomes, infection (20.16%, n = 49) was the most common, followed by malocclusion (13.99%, n = 34) and plate loosening (13.99%, n = 34). Transient paraesthesia of the lower lip occurred in 4.93%, while mandibular deviation/deflection, pain in the temporomandibular joint, and malunion were less frequent. No cases of non-union were reported. (Table 5)

Table 5: Complications of maxillofacial fracture treatment in the study subjects

S. No.	Post-operative complications	Percentage (%)	Number (n)
1.	Transient Paresthesia (Lower lip)	4.93	12
2.	Malocclusion	13.99	34
3.	Mandibular deviation/deflection	4.11	10
4.	Infection	20.16	49
5.	Pain in TMJ	2.05	5
6.	Malunion	2.88	7
7.	Non-union	0	0
8.	Plate Loosening	13.99	34
9.	Uneventful healing	37.86	92

The chi-square analysis ($\chi^2 = 382.7$, $df = 8$, $p < 0.001$) revealed a statistically significant difference in the distribution of complications, indicating that certain outcomes—particularly infection and malocclusion—occurred at significantly higher rates.

Overall, the results suggest that the majority of patients experienced uneventful recovery, while infection and malocclusion remain the predominant post-operative concerns following maxillofacial fracture management.

Discussion

The present three-year retrospective clinical study was conducted to evaluate the pattern, etiology, mode of intubation, associated complications, and treatment outcomes of maxillofacial trauma cases reported to a tertiary care hospital in central Uttar Pradesh.

The mean age of the study population was 39.9 ± 12.4 years, with the highest incidence (32.5%) observed in the 26–35-year age group. This aligns with findings from previous studies, which suggest that young adults are most commonly affected by maxillofacial trauma due to greater outdoor exposure and risk-taking behaviour. The male predominance (68.7%) noted in this study is consistent with the observations of Kumar et al. (2023)⁶ and Pandey et al. (2013)⁷, who reported male involvement in 89.62% of cases in their respective studies.

The etiology of maxillofacial trauma differs across various geographical regions. In developing countries,⁸ road traffic accidents remain the most common cause, a finding consistent with several previous studies.^{9,10}

Among maxillary and midfacial fractures, zygomaticomaxillary complex (ZMC) fractures were the most common (67.07%), followed by Le Fort II (20.16%) and Le Fort III (7.8%) fractures. In cases involving the mandible, condylar (31.27%) and parasymphysis (27.98%) fractures were the most frequently observed. These results are in agreement with the findings of Gurung et al. (2019)¹¹ and Shekar et al. (2008)¹², who also reported a higher incidence of ZMC and condylar fractures.

Regarding the mode of intubation, nasotracheal intubation was performed in 86.06% of the study subjects, while submental intubation was used in 11.93% of cases. All patients with panfacial fractures underwent submental intubation. These findings are consistent with those of Hall C et al. (2003)¹³ and Vasishta et al. (2010)¹⁴, who reported similar trends in the use of nasotracheal and submental intubation techniques.

Infection (20.16%), malocclusion (13.99%), and plate loosening (13.99%) were identified as the most common postoperative complications. These findings are comparable to those of Kumar et al. (2023)¹⁵, who also reported infection and plate loosening as frequent postoperative issues. The relatively high incidence of infection in the present study highlights the need for strict adherence to infection control protocols and meticulous postoperative care. Previous studies have shown varying complication rates; for example, Shekar et al. (2008)¹⁶ reported an overall complication rate of 40%, with infection and malocclusion being the most prevalent. In contrast, the current study demonstrated a 37.86% rate of uneventful healing, indicating generally favourable outcomes. Nevertheless, the elevated infection rate observed underscores the importance of enhancing postoperative management strategies.

Conclusion:

The findings of this study support existing literature on the demographic and etiological trends of maxillofacial trauma. The high incidence of road traffic accidents (RTAs) and related complications highlights the necessity for targeted preventive interventions, such as road safety awareness programs and optimized surgical protocols. Further research is needed to identify the underlying factors contributing to postoperative complications and to develop strategies aimed at improving patient outcomes.

Ethical Consideration: Not required (based on hospital and autopsy records)

Conflict of interest: Nil

Source of Funding: Self

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